

Advancing Healthcare Consent Management: The PAROMA-MED Platform’s Integration of User-Centered Interfaces, FHIR, and the EU Data Space Connector

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Abstract. The increasing complexity of healthcare data management requires advanced solutions to ensure privacy, security, and regulatory compliance. Consent management, in particular, is a critical component of patient-centered care in the digital age, as patients need complete control over how their sensitive health information is accessed and used. This paper presents the PAROMA-MED platform, which introduces a user-centric consent management framework designed to improve transparency and trust in healthcare data exchanges. By integrating technologies such as the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard, the EU Data Space Connector, and an intuitive user interface, PAROMA-MED empowers patients to control their health data. We explore the technical and user interaction aspects of the platform, highlighting how it addresses the challenges of consent management while ensuring regulatory compliance with GDPR. This paper discusses the implications of these technologies for improving healthcare delivery and fostering patient engagement.

Keywords: Adaptive and personalized interfaces, anonymity and privacy, privacy and online security, UX (user experience) and usability, e-health.

1 Introduction

The growing digitization of healthcare has led to an exponential increase in the volume and sensitivity of patient data being processed, shared, and stored. As a result, ensuring secure, compliant, and user-friendly data management systems has become a pressing concern for healthcare platforms. The PAROMA-MED [14] platform addresses these challenges by integrating advanced technologies for consent management, data interoperability, and privacy awareness into its framework. Central to this is its focus on human-computer interaction (HCI) principles, ensuring that even nontechnical stakeholders, such as patients, can intuitively interact with the system to manage their data preferences and understand their rights.

Consent management in healthcare presents unique challenges [1, 19]. Patients must retain control over their data, but healthcare providers and researchers need timely access to these data to deliver personalized care and drive medical innovation. This balance act requires systems that are both secure and transparent. The PAROMA-MED platform introduces a solution that integrates:

- User-Centered Interfaces: Allowing patients and other stakeholders to visualize and manage their data consents dynamically.
- FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) [4]: Enabling standardized and interoperable data management.
- EU Data Space Connector [7]: Ensure secure, consent-compliant data sharing between entities in a federated ecosystem.

The platform takes an innovative approach by embedding these technologies within a privacy-centric and security-aware environment. It is designed not only to comply with strict regulations like GDPR [3], but also to empower users through dynamic consent models, privacy dashboards, and real-time monitoring of data usage. This paper explores the integration of these technologies into PAROMA-MED, focusing on the role of HCI in the advancement of healthcare through better consent management.

Furthermore, the platform’s design supports emerging healthcare paradigms such as federated learning and collaborative research, where patient data remain decentralized but accessible under strict usage controls. The challenges addressed include

- Simplifying complex consent management workflows.
- Providing situational awareness through intuitive visual interfaces.
- Securing data sharing across various distributed systems.

1.1 Background and Related Work

Consent management in healthcare has become a focal point of research and development as data-intensive technologies, such as AI and machine learning, transform the field. Patients’ ability to control how their sensitive health data

are accessed and used is fundamental to maintaining trust and ensuring compliance with stringent regulatory frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe [1, 5, 15]. At the same time, healthcare providers and researchers need interoperable systems that facilitate seamless data sharing and collaboration to improve patient outcomes and advance medical research.

Existing Challenges in Healthcare Consent Management. Traditional consent management systems in healthcare are often static and rigid, failing to provide the flexibility needed in modern, dynamic healthcare settings. Patients often lack visibility into how their data are used after giving consent, and systems often do not support granular, purpose-specific, or time-bound consents. These limitations lead to potential privacy violations and decreased patient trust. For researchers and providers, the lack of interoperability between systems creates barriers to accessing critical data while adhering to consent policies.

Furthermore, advances in federated healthcare ecosystems, such as cross-border data sharing initiatives and collaborative research projects, highlight the need for consent management systems that are scalable, secure, and adaptable to complex data sharing scenarios [11]. Technologies such as FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) have made strides in addressing interoperability challenges, but integrating privacy and consent capabilities into these frameworks remains an ongoing area of research.

Advances in Consent Management Technologies. Recent research has explored several approaches to enhance consent management in healthcare:

Dynamic Consent Models These models provide patients with ongoing control over their data, enabling them to update their consents in real time. Dynamic consent has been shown to improve transparency and patient engagement compared to traditional one-time consent processes [21, 18].

Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing Advances in privacy-preserving techniques, such as data anonymization, pseudonymization, and homomorphic encryption, address privacy risks associated with data sharing. However, these techniques often require integration with consent frameworks to effectively enforce patient preferences [22].

User-Centered Interfaces Studies in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) have demonstrated the importance of designing interfaces that are intuitive, accessible, and engaging [10]. Interfaces that allow users to visualize data flows, consent status, and privacy policies have been identified as critical enablers of patient trust and adoption.

The Role of Interoperability and Standards. Standards such as FHIR have become a cornerstone of healthcare data management by allowing the exchange

of structured data between diverse systems [6, 16]. However, while FHIR supports data interoperability, it does not inherently include mechanisms for managing consent or enforcing privacy policies. Researchers have proposed extensions to the FHIR standard to incorporate consent resources, enabling systems to store and share consent information alongside health data. The EU Data Space Connector, another emerging technology, facilitates secure and interoperable data sharing across organizational and national boundaries, adhering to strict usage policies [8].

PAROMA-MED in the Context of Related Work. The PAROMA-MED platform builds on these advances by integrating user-centered interfaces, FHIR, and the EU Data Space Connector into a unified system that addresses both technical and user-interaction challenges in consent management. PAROMA-MED combines these elements into a comprehensive solution that is **interoperable**, using FHIR for data standardization and the EU Data Space Connector for federated data sharing; **patient-centric**, incorporating a dynamic consent management system with an intuitive GUI to empower users; and **secure**, using state-of-the-art security measures, including zero trust architecture via OpenZiti [13] and continuous monitoring using Wazuh [20].

Located at the intersection of HCI and healthcare data management, the platform addresses the gaps in current systems. It emphasizes not only technical robustness, but also usability and transparency, aligning with the latest research in dynamic consent, privacy-preserving technologies, and interoperable frameworks. This document builds on these foundations, exploring the integrated approach of PAROMA-MED that can redefine consent management of healthcare care and advance both patient empowerment and data-driven innovation.

2 PAROMA-MED Platform Overview

PAROMA-MED is an integrated healthcare platform designed to meet the needs of modern healthcare data management, with a particular focus on patient privacy and consent management. The platform provides a secure, interoperable environment for managing sensitive health data, featuring:

User-Centered Interface. A central component of PAROMA-MED is its user-friendly interface, which allows patients to easily manage consent preferences. This interface was designed following the principles of human-computer interaction (HCI) to ensure that patients with varying degrees of technical expertise can understand and control their data.

FHIR integration. The platform leverages the FHIR standard to ensure seamless data exchange between various healthcare systems. FHIR enables the platform to manage patient data consistently, facilitating interoperability with existing electronic health record systems and third-party applications [16].

EU Data Space Connector. To ensure secure, GDPR-compliant data sharing between different healthcare entities and across borders, PAROMA-MED integrates the EU Data Space Connector. This connector allows the platform to exchange patient data securely while maintaining patient control over how their data are used.

Fig. 1. PAROMA-MED platform overview

The PAROMA-MED platform described in Figure 1 is designed to enhance privacy-sensitive, secure, and interoperable data sharing in the healthcare sector. Addresses the challenges of managing sensitive medical data while ensuring compliance with GDPR and other privacy regulations. The platform enables patients, healthcare providers, and researchers to securely share and access health data through a federated, consent-driven system.

At its core, PAROMA-MED integrates advanced privacy-preserving technologies, consent management, and security controls. Using Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) for structured and standardized data exchange, ensuring seamless interoperability between different healthcare systems. The EU Data Space Connector facilitates controlled, policy-driven data sharing across healthcare institutions, enabling cross-border collaborations while maintaining strong privacy safeguards.

The platform follows a zero-trust security model, incorporating tools such as OpenZiti for secure networking, Wazuh for real-time security monitoring, and Open Policy Agent (OPA) [12] for dynamic policy enforcement. Its Situational Awareness GUI provides users with a transparent and intuitive interface to monitor, grant, and revoke data-sharing consents dynamically.

By combining advanced security measures, dynamic consent management, and decentralized data governance, PAROMA-MED ensures that patients retain full control over their data, while healthcare providers and researchers can securely access the information they need to advance medical innovation. The approach of the platform aligns with the broader European Health Data Space (EHDS) [2] initiative, supporting trusted, secure, and privacy-aware digital healthcare ecosystems.

2.1 User Interface for Consent Management

One of the key innovations of the PAROMA-MED platform is its user-centered approach to consent management. The interface is designed to be intuitive, allowing patients to easily view, modify, and revoke consent for the use of their health data. The platform provides clear explanations of what each consent option entails, ensuring that patients are fully informed about how their data will be used. This approach is in line with best practices for HCI, focusing on clarity, ease of use, and accessibility.

Fig. 2. Example view of the PAROMA-MED UI for consent management.

The PAROMA-MED Consent Management Interface seen in Figure 2 provides a structured and intuitive user experience to manage consents for health-

care data. Designed to ensure transparency, control, and ease of interaction, the interface enables users to efficiently manage their privacy preferences in a healthcare setting.

On the left, a dark blue vertical navigation bar provides structured access to different sections, including Consent Management, Notifications, Compliance Dashboard, and Administration. These sections allow users to navigate seamlessly between managing consents, receiving updates, monitoring compliance with regulations such as GDPR, and handling system configurations. The main panel prominently displays the Consent Management Overview, categorizing consents into three distinct groups: allowed, pending, and denied. Consents that have been granted appear in green, while those awaiting user action are highlighted in yellow, and explicitly denied consents are marked in red. Users can explore the details within each category and modify their preferences using a dedicated button.

Below the overview, the interface presents personal information fields such as sex, name, and birth date, each with a visible consent status. Pending consents are indicated with a yellow warning icon, while denied access appears in red. Users are provided with "Allow" and "Deny" buttons for immediate action, ensuring dynamic control over data-sharing preferences. Similarly, the Imaging Studies section in this example extends the management of granular consent to medical imaging data, detailing specific attributes such as modality, imaging metadata, and unique identifiers. Each attribute carries a status marker that indicates whether data are allowed, pending, or denied, providing users with a complete view of their privacy settings.

The overall design of the interface emphasizes clarity and transparency by color coded consent categories, allowing users to interpret their data sharing settings at a glance. By integrating action-driven elements such as instant approval or denial buttons and providing fine-tuned privacy control at the attribute level, the interface ensures that users maintain a high degree of oversight over their health data.

To enhance usability further, tool tips or contextual explanations will be added to technical fields such as "FrameOfReferenceUID" to support non technical users. A batch approval option could also streamline the process for users who need to approve or deny multiple consents simultaneously. In addition, integrating an audit log and consent history improves transparency by enabling users to track changes over time.

The PAROMA-MED Consent Management UI successfully balances functionality with user-centric design, making it an effective tool for managing healthcare data privacy. Through its structured approach and real-time interaction capabilities, it empowers users with clear and actionable insights into their data-sharing preferences while maintaining compliance with evolving privacy regulations.

2.2 FHIR for Interoperable Consent Data

The integration of FHIR into PAROMA-MED is crucial to ensure that consent preferences are not only captured, but also honored across different systems. The FHIR consent resource allows the platform to model, store, and share consent data in a standardized format, ensuring that any system connected to the platform respects the patient’s choices. This interoperability enables seamless transitions between care providers and institutions while ensuring that patient consent is consistently enforced.

Fig. 3. UML diagram of the FHIR consent resource definition. Source: <https://hl7.org/fhir/consent.html>.

The UML diagram of the FHIR consent resource in Figure 3 outlines the structure and relationships within the consent resource, which models how patients grant or deny permission for data access and use in healthcare settings.

At the core of the model is the Consent (DomainResource) entity, which includes attributes such as identifier, status, and category to define the consent’s purpose and life-cycle. The subject represents the patient or group for whom the consent is applied, while references to the grantee, grantor, manager, and controller specify the individuals or organizations involved in managing the consent. The decision field determines whether access is allowed or denied, while policyBasis and policyText link to relevant policy documents governing data use.

The verification component ensures that the consent has been validated, capturing details such as verification status, verifier identity, and verification

date. The Provision section specifies the conditions under which consent applies, including allowed actions (e.g., access, disclose), security labels, purpose of use, and data restrictions such as specific document types or resource categories. The ProvisionData structure defines the meaning of the data covered and references the relevant records.

The ProvisionActor component details the roles and entities involved in performing consented actions, defining who can access or process the data. Multiple provision elements allow for complex consent rules, enabling organizations to model conditional, time-bound, and purpose-limited data access policies.

In general, the FHIR consent resource provides a standardized and interoperable framework for managing patient consent in compliance with privacy regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA, ensuring transparency, enforceability, and fine-grained control over access to healthcare data.

2.3 EU Data Space Connector for Secure Data Sharing

The EU Data Space Connector provides the backbone for secure data exchanges across borders and between different healthcare providers. With the Connector, PAROMA-MED ensures that only authorized parties can access patient data and that data sharing adheres to the agreed-upon consent policies. The Connector supports fine-grained usage control, allowing patients to specify how their data can be used, for what purpose, and for how long, while complying with the GDPR.

In modern healthcare, secure and compliant data sharing is essential for effective medical collaboration, research, and patient-centered care. However, traditional data-sharing models pose significant challenges related to privacy, security, consent management, and interoperability. The EU Data Space Connector addresses these issues by acting as a trusted mediator, ensuring that data transactions adhere to well-defined policies and usage control mechanisms.

The EDSC follows the International Data Spaces (IDS) architecture, providing a standardized interface that supports trusted, auditable, and consent-driven data sharing. This approach enables healthcare providers, researchers, and policy makers to exchange health data securely without centralizing them, mitigating the risks related to data breaches, unauthorized access, and regulatory non-compliance.

Integration with PAROMA-MED for Privacy-Preserving Health Data Exchange. In the PAROMA-MED ecosystem, the EU Data Space Connector serves as the primary access control and policy enforcement mechanism for federated data exchanges. It integrates with various components, including:

- FHIR-based Health Data Repositories: Ensuring interoperability through structured data standards.
- Consent Management System: Implementing patient-consensus data sharing policies, ensuring compliance with GDPR and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) framework.

- Open Policy Agent (OPA) for Dynamic Policy Enforcement: Translating usage policies (e.g., ODRL-based rules [17]) into real-time access control decisions.
- Zero-Trust Security via OpenZiti: Ensuring secure networking for sensitive data transmissions.

By integrating these elements, PAROMA-MED creates a secure, decentralized, and interoperable data-sharing framework, where all data exchanges are governed by fine-grained access control policies, transparent audit trails, and automated compliance checks.

Policy-Driven Data Governance and Usage Control. A key feature of the EU Data Space Connector is its ability to enforce policy-driven governance. This means that data are only shared under preapproved conditions, defined by stakeholders such as patients, regulatory bodies, and healthcare institutions. These policies can be encoded using ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language) and enforced in real time through the Open Policy Agent (OPA). These governance principles are as follows.

- Consent-Based Access Control: Patients have the ability to set fine-grained permissions on who can access their data, for what purpose, and for how long. The EDSC ensures that all data requests are validated against these policies.
- Purpose-Driven Data Access: Data usage must be explicitly tied to predefined purposes, such as clinical research, diagnostics, or public health monitoring. Unauthorized secondary use of data is automatically blocked.
- Secure Data Provenance and Auditability: All transactions are logged on a tamper-proof audit trail, ensuring transparency and accountability for data-sharing activities.

These governance principles align with GDPR, the European Health Data Space (EHDS) framework, and the Data Governance Act (DGA), ensuring that data remain under the control of their rightful owners while being accessible for legitimate, consented purposes.

Enabling Cross-Border Data Exchange and Federated Learning. One of the most powerful applications of the EU Data Space Connector in PAROMA-MED is its role in enabling cross-border data exchange and federated learning [9]. In traditional machine learning approaches, data need to be centralized to train models. However, this presents significant privacy and security risks, particularly in healthcare.

With federated learning, the EU Data Space Connector allows AI models to be trained across multiple healthcare institutions without moving raw patient data. Instead of sending data to a central location, machine learning models travel to the data, train locally, and then exchange only aggregated, anonymized

insights. This privacy-preserving AI approach is particularly valuable for **personalized medicine** and **predictive analytics**, **epidemiological studies** and **public health monitoring**, **clinical trials** and **drug discovery**. By orchestrating data access across distributed datasets, the EU Data Space Connector facilitates large-scale AI training while maintaining data sovereignty and compliance.

Security and Compliance Considerations. To ensure that all data-sharing activities meet the highest security and regulatory standards, the EU Data Space Connector in PAROMA-MED is equipped with the following:

- End-to-End Encryption: Secure transmission of data using TLS.
- Zero-Trust Access Control: Every data request is authenticated and authorized before access is granted, ensuring that even trusted users have only the minimal access required.
- Automated Compliance Checks: Wazuh continuously monitors the system for security risks, unauthorized access attempts, and GDPR violations, providing real-time alerts and compliance reporting.

3 Implementation and Results

The PAROMA-MED platform has been implemented as a modular solution, allowing different healthcare systems to seamlessly integrate consent management. Through the combination of FHIR’s standardized data structure and the EU Data Space Connector’s secure data exchange capabilities, the platform ensures that patient consent is enforceable and traceable between different institutions.

In a typical PAROMA-MED data sharing scenario as depicted in Figure 4, a researcher conducting an imaging study needs access to patient data that has been advertised through the Data Space Connector (DSC). To begin, the researcher queries the DSC for available data sets within the PAROMA-MED Data Platform, which aggregates and manages patient health records. The Data Platform returns metadata describing the available datasets, allowing the researcher to identify relevant data for the study.

Once the researcher selects a dataset, they submit a request to access patient data. The Data Platform, before granting access, validates the request by forwarding it to the Abstraction API for the DSC, which ensures that all access requests comply with predefined data-sharing policies and governance rules. The DSC also checks whether the necessary patient consent exists by querying the FHIR Server, which manages structured healthcare data and consent records. If prior consent has not been granted, the DSC triggers a consent request.

The patient is then notified via the PAROMA-MED User Interface (UI), which presents a detailed request explaining how their data would be used in the imaging study. The patient reviews the request and makes an informed decision on whether to approve or deny access to the data. If the patient grants consent, the UI updates the DSC, which then stores the updated consent record

Fig. 4. PAROMA-MED data-sharing scenario.

on the FHIR server, ensuring that all access permissions are properly logged and enforced.

Following successful consent validation, the Data Platform grants the researcher access to the approved dataset for use in the imaging study. This workflow ensures that patients retain full control over their data while allowing researchers to access health information in a secure, compliant, and privacy-aware manner. The integration of the Data Space Connector, FHIR, and policy-driven access control ensures that all data exchanges align with GDPR and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulations, creating a trustworthy and ethical framework for medical research and data-driven innovation.

Early user studies conducted with healthcare professionals and patients showed positive feedback regarding the interface’s clarity and ease of use. Patients expressed a higher degree of trust in the sharing of their data due to the transparency and control provided by the platform. Healthcare providers found that integration with existing FHIR-based systems was straightforward and the use of the Data Space Connector enabled secure collaborations between institutions without compromising patient privacy.

4 Discussion

PAROMA-MED addresses several challenges in the management of consent in modern healthcare care, particularly the balance between data accessibility and privacy. By integrating FHIR and the EU Data Space Connector, the platform ensures that patients retain control over their data while still benefiting from the advanced healthcare services enabled by data sharing. Furthermore, the platform’s user interface demonstrates how human-centered design can empower

patients, making the consent management process transparent and accessible. As PAROMA-MED continues to evolve, future work will focus on expanding its capabilities to include more complex consent scenarios, such as dynamic consent models and machine-readable consent policies for AI-driven healthcare applications. In addition, further research will explore the scalability of the platform in larger healthcare ecosystems and assess long-term user satisfaction and trust. The PAROMA-MED platform represents a significant advance in healthcare consent management, providing patients with greater control and transparency over their health data. Using technologies such as FHIR, the EU Data Space Connector, and a user-centered interface, PAROMA-MED ensures that consent is managed efficiently and in compliance with regulations such as GDPR. This approach not only improves patient privacy, but also facilitates more secure and interoperable healthcare systems, advancing the goals of Health 4.0.

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